
Breaking the Bubble. Elements for a Research Program.

Sacha Raoult*

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Abstract : This paper introduces an intellectual framework dedicated to the study of personal transformation. It outlines three orientations. First, the project responds to a growing sense that contemporary life is marked by profound shifts whose causes and direction remain uncertain, prompting renewed academic attention to the dynamics of change. Second, it promotes an interdisciplinary, practice-oriented approach that encourages dialogue across academic fields and with practitioners, in order to avoid the isolation that often accompanies disciplinary boundaries. Third, it places religious and spiritual symbolism at the center of this reflection, since concepts drawn from religious traditions continue to inform modern analyses of human behavior while remaining insufficiently integrated into many academic domains.

Keywords: metanoia; change; religious studies; interdisciplinarity

First, I would like to express my gratitude. Thanks to the Sciences Po team for their help in organizing this conference, to my colleague Alexis for his considerable efforts in preparing

this event, and to all of you, participants and listeners, for being here today for this study day marking the launch of our center dedicated to the interdisciplinary study of personal

* Aix-Marseille Université, Institut Universitaire de France, Chair of Transitions (Université Mohammed VI Polytech). Correspondence should be addressed to sacha.raoult@univ-amu.fr. Authors agree to [FOSN Code of conduct](#) including that any conflict of interest must be disclosed.

transformation.

I'll be brief, as we've planned a double introduction, and I don't want to monopolize time in a day already rich in interventions. Before Alexis takes the floor to expand on the notion of change and personal transformation, which will be at the heart of this day, I'd like to share the threefold motivation I have :

- On the importance of the notion of change and transformation, which forms the foundation of this project.

- On an interdisciplinary and practice-oriented approach, which is essential for tackling these complex issues.

- On a specific interdisciplinary approach, in which the religious-spiritual sciences occupy a central place in a dialogue with all the human sciences.

On the notion of change and transformation

On the question of change and transformation, I don't wish to encroach on Alexis's presentation, which will explore in detail the various dimensions that this notion can cover. I would, however, like to share a personal observation. I was pleasantly surprised by the enthusiasm generated by this line of thinking among the speakers. The question of personal change, individual transformation and social change has clearly struck a chord with you, and I'm delighted to see the scale of the positive response that has enabled us

to organize this day.

I don't pretend to explain the precise reasons for this enthusiasm, but I can say that it partly reflects a shared intuition: that we are currently living through a period of major transformation. This transformation is palpable, although its direction and drivers remain uncertain. Is it driven by technology? By internal company dynamics? By ideological changes? Does it bring hope, or should we be concerned? What I can see is that it is permeating our lives in a far more profound way than we were able to perceive some fifteen years ago. That's why I think it's essential for academic researchers to get to grips with this subject at this particular time.

On the interdisciplinary approach and its challenges

With regard to the interdisciplinary approach underpinning this project, I'm speaking here as an academic. I believe we are all aware of the risks we face: that of being locked in a double bubble.

- a. The first bubble is that which isolates us from the practitioner, from everyday life - in short, from what is often referred to by generic terms in the academic world. This bubble, the famous "ivory tower", although it confers a certain autonomy on the university, enabling it to free itself from prejudice and false evidence, can also become a trap. It risks cutting us off from concrete concerns and the realities of the world, and, in some

cases, leading us towards an intellectualism that is counter-productive to a genuine intellectual approach.

Faced with this, there have always been impulses within the university to break down this barrier. We can think, for example, of major movements such as Michael Burawoy's declaration in favor of a public sociology, or very specific initiatives such as the work carried out in France in fields like criminology, with the Centre sur la délinquance des mineurs de Vaucresson. These initiatives testify to a recurring desire to establish a richer dialogue between theory and practice.

It is precisely this kind of impetus that drives the approach and positioning of our center. We want to build bridges between the university and the outside world, between intellect and action, so that this interdisciplinary approach is truly rooted in human and social realities.

b. Within this first bubble, which sometimes separates the academic world from practice, lies another series of bubbles: those of the academic disciplines themselves. Traditions, research programs and theoretical frameworks often develop autonomously, creating barriers that sometimes isolate these fields from one another.

The second impetus behind the creation of this center is therefore to provide a pretext and a space for these disciplinary bubbles to communicate with each other around this topic. The

aim is to create a place for dialogue that is as heterogeneous as possible, without breaking down communication channels.

Of course, academic disciplines and traditions are not isolated by chance. Andrew Abbott masterfully demonstrates their usefulness: they facilitate exchanges within their respective communities, structure the job market and limit the risk of misunderstandings. So, if my experience of interdisciplinarity can serve as an indicator, I'm sure that today there will be misunderstandings. When we come from different traditions, we don't always use words in the same way, nor frame problems in the same way.

But it is precisely in this friction that the richness of interdisciplinarity lies. The history of science and the social sciences is full of examples where disciplinary hybridization has led to significant advances. Think of the role of empirical sociology in the philosophy of law, the influence of psychodynamics on sociology, or the contributions of economics to historical analysis. These cross-fertilizations between disciplines are often at the origin of the most fertile renewals.

It is this dynamic that I hope to see manifested in this center. Together, through our exchanges, we can contribute to enriching perspectives and strengthening the relevance of our common work.

On using spiritual and religious symbolism in the human sciences

The final choice that underpins the idea of this center through the choice of the term Metanoia is that of placing spiritual and religious symbolism at the heart of this interdisciplinary and social questioning of change.

The intellectual of secular modernity is, in a way, haunted by symbolism and religious analogies. I'm not just referring to modern debates on free will, or to psychoanalytical questioning on the partition of the unconscious, which are very direct extensions of theological questioning, as Henri Ellenberger, for example, has shown. I'm talking about the constant tendency in the social sciences to draw metaphors and analytical frameworks from the religious sciences in order to understand the human condition.

Take, for example, Karl Marx's concept of "commodity fetishism", which analyzes capitalism as a form of totemic religion, or the historian Yuri Slezkine's study of communism as a prophetic religion. These examples show the extent to which religious metaphors nourish the social sciences, whether in the form of analogy or structuring paradigm.

But these borrowings raise an essential question: are they simply metaphors? Can they be put to good use? For this, it is crucial to establish a solid dialogue between the human sciences, giving a central place to the

religious sciences, which alone enable us to understand the appropriateness of this analogy. Yet, paradoxically, what I'm discovering in my own field, and perhaps more widely in the classical human sciences, is, on the contrary, a significant distance, sometimes even ignorance, towards the contributions of the religious sciences.

In my field, criminology, this separation is particularly striking. Who, in classical criminology, really knows the extent of Christianity's influence on our penal norms, including in more recent reform trends such as restorative justice, which has one of its origins in Anabaptist communities? Similarly, when it comes to delinquent behavior, there is a notable lack of understanding of the effects of religious practice or religious conversion on such behavior. Byron Johnson, for example, speaks of a veritable taboo in this area. While criminologists regularly question a multitude of variables, the study of religious programs on recidivism, for example, remains marginal and often marginalized.

At the very least, I think we have a lot to learn from the issues raised by the religious sciences. Anyone interested in the processes of human change, whether individual or collective, could benefit from a dialogue with these disciplines. Thus, the question that best sums up my vision of the problem of Metanoia is: can religious conversion, in particular, serve as a matrix for a general

epistemology of personal change, at both individual and social levels? Rather than being limited to a simplified analogy, this paradigm

could be enriched by genuine interdisciplinary collaboration with those who study these phenomena in depth.

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